

Spreading awareness cybersecurity via storytelling: a Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

Contribution: This Systematic Literature Review (SLR) aims to investigate how storytelling can effectively convey cybersecurity awareness for specific target groups in education, from different age groups.

Background: Cybersecurity is increasingly pervasive, impacting nearly everyone globally. Therefore, there's a critical need for widespread education on the risks and consequences of daily technology use.

Research Questions: **RQ1:** *Are there any methods to approach the topic of cybersecurity without age constraints?* **ZARQA:** *What type of technology used emerges from our review?* **RQ3:** *Which are the major outcomes of the proposed initiatives?*

Methodology: We use PRISMA guidelines (Page et al., 2021) with $n = 53$ papers published until December 2023 identified and $n = 18$ final relevant papers.

Findings: This review identified delivery methods (Chowdhury et al., 2021), within the research field of technology-enhanced learning, that address, by the introduction of storytelling approach, the spread of cybersecurity education, leading to increased awareness and engagement on cybersecurity issues. It confirms that traditional forms of education focusing solely on knowledge transmission are not well suited for developing learning and understanding in a highly dynamic area such as cybersecurity. These delivery methods aim at developing cybersecurity awareness through the storytelling approach, expanding the notion of "being secure" to that of "acting securely".

Keywords: Digital Storytelling, Cybersecurity, Awareness, Engagement, Learning and Replication Package.

1 Introduction

Cybersecurity is increasingly affecting people worldwide, emphasizing the critical need for widespread education about the dangers and consequences of technology use, given its pervasive presence in daily life. Cybersecurity as a learning domain for all, however, still suffers from a seeming randomness of educational approaches and their evaluation. Without claiming to have the complete overview of what Cybersecurity Education (CSE) is, or should be, about, our experience as learning and computer scientists, involved in several EU-funded cybersecurity projects, allows us to identify a number of characteristics of the domain. This will lead us to propose a set of criteria for CSE that could serve as a starting point for identifying and evaluating various CSE approaches. These criteria will then be used to review a small set of papers of CSE, that start from a promising educational approach, to assess the usefulness of these criteria and the potential impact of this approach. This paper means to invoke discussion and further elaboration of what can be considered valid approaches to CSE, for specific target groups in education, from different age groups.

1.1 A vision on cybersecurity education

To be able to develop suitable criteria, we propose a view of cybersecurity as a learning domain, not as a purely technical field, but as involving a range of socio-technical issues, by which we underline the importance of understanding contextual and human factors. Within this view, we propose the following characteristics of cybersecurity as a learning domain: (1) It requires a holistic view: by not only focusing on technology, but also on contextual, organisational, societal, legal, economical, and psychological aspects that influence security (Vasileiou et al., 2019); (2) It requires a collaborative view: all people have a role and responsibility in cybersecurity, and these roles are interdependent during resolution of cyberthreats, but also in prevention of such threats (Furnell et al., 2022); (3) It requires a dynamic view: the domain is not static, the field is constantly changing (Schaberreiter et al., 2022). Traditional forms of education focusing on knowledge transmission are not suited for developing learning and understanding in a highly dynamic area such as cybersecurity. We need forms of education that aim at the

development of cybersecurity awareness: being able to understand and act in a variety of situations. The action component of awareness is crucial here: because technology has invaded every aspect of our lives, and continues to expand its pervasiveness, we must learn how to act safely and responsibly with technology. Cybersecurity awareness expands the notion of “being secure” to that of “acting securely”.

In this paper, we analyse a set of educational programs for cybersecurity in which storytelling is used. We propose to evaluate the extent to which the learning activities, proposed in these programs, present the cybersecurity domain with respect to a particular **context**, discuss the issues and events as **multi-disciplinary**, concern the roles and responsibilities of the persons in the story in **action**, and include **reflection** on lessons learned.

Roadmaps. The structure of our work is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the research methodology applied in this study to conduct a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) and the Research Questions (RQs) that guided the study. Section 3 displays findings related to the RQs. Finally, Section 4 presents the conclusions and further research of this study.

2 Methodology

Users face rising cybersecurity risks due to a lack of education. Children are especially vulnerable. The European strategy "Safety and Security from Childhood" launched in May 2022, aims to protect and empower children online. The Better Internet for Children (BIK+) Commission, n.d.(a) initiative emphasizes the need for cybersecurity education, especially for children.

Addressed by this study, the RQs are the following: **RQ1:** *Are there any methods to approach the topic of cybersecurity without age constraints?*; **RQ2:** *What type of technology used emerges from our review?*; **RQ3:** *Which are the major outcomes of the proposed initiatives?*

This literature review is based on the approach “Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses” (PRISMA) (Page et al., 2021), and proceeded as a recapped diagram of the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) in Fig. 1. The overall objective is to consider approaches and toolkits to introduce, learn, or engage learners of any age concerning cybersecurity. We considered cybersecurity and storytelling as keywords, also considering alternative forms of the same terms. As a result, the performed query is the following: (cybersecurity OR “cyber security” OR “cyber-security”) AND storytelling.

The search was conducted using specific terms in titles, keywords, or abstracts, up to December 2023. Major databases

like Scopus, ACM Digital Library, and IEEEExplore¹ were utilized due to their coverage of relevant conferences and journals in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI), Child-Computer Interaction (CCI), and Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL). Initially, $n = 41$ records were identified from these databases, with an additional 12 papers found through other sources, e.g., by expert contacts, and hand searching in major conference abstracts related to HCI, CCI, and TEL, totaling $n = 53$ after removing duplicates. The screening process began with the set eligibility criteria, focusing on peer-reviewed papers applying storytelling to cybersecurity. Two researchers independently screened articles based on titles and abstracts, recording results in a spreadsheet as relevant (1) or irrelevant (-1). Discordant opinions were discussed until a consensus was reached. This process resulted in $n = 18$ papers deemed relevant for the review, which focused on storytelling approaches for cybersecurity awareness and education across various learner age groups and contexts, excluding papers analyzing or monitoring vulnerabilities through log narration.

3 Results of the Literature Review: Cybersecurity Education

We come up with $n = 18$ relevant contributions, which have been classified according to the nature of the used toolkits. It lets us investigate the use of technology-enabling approaches to teach cybersecurity via storytelling. Moreover, we classified relevant contributions according to the performed or envisioned assessment, by distinguishing approaches to engage, introduce, improve awareness, or let participants learn about cybersecurity. It goes in the direction of investigating to what extent storytelling can be used to go beyond the introductory stage and effectively enable learning. We also classified relevant contributions according to the used approach distinguishing game-based approaches from the use of narratives and comics. By considering approaches and target groups at the meantime we can check if any approach is independent by age and can be easily reused to approach participants of different age ranges. In Fig. 2 The study identifies three primary target groups: K-12 Learners, Graduate (G), and Undergraduate (UG) students, with an additional category labeled ‘Other participants.’ This category includes teachers evaluating Digital Storytelling methodology (Khalid et al., 2020), vulnerable groups needing customizable technology (Heiden et al., 2023), and laypersons who use the Internet daily at home. Incidents are classified using the eCSIRT.net mkVI reference taxonomy, with any unclassified incidents grouped under "Other" in the according to (Commission,

¹ <https://www.scopus.com/>,
<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/>

<https://dl.acm.org/>,

Figure 1. PRISMA workflow for the SLR.

n.d.[b]). The "Delivery Methods" column classifies all tools according to (Chowdhury et al., 2021): "Game-based" (e.g., Serious games for Cyber Security awareness and training), Video-based (e.g., educational videos), and Simulation and virtualization-based (e.g., Simulation platforms, etc.). The "Tool/Book name" column will indicate the tool's name or the

reference documentation. A further classification concerns whether it is an authoring story (i.e. "Authoring" column); the specific technology (i.e. web-based, desktop and laptop computers, social robot, etc.) used is documented in the "Technology" column. The rows highlighted in yellow indicate works that have not conducted any experiments.

3.1 RQ1: Cybersecurity Educational genre.

To address our RQ1, as illustrated in Fig. 2, three main delivery methods according to (Chowdhury et al., 2021) emerge: game-based, simulation and virtualization-based, and video-based typologies. Each method incorporates elements of storytelling with the aim of engaging users and raising awareness of cyber threats. Digital online games for teaching cybersecurity emerge from our study and are also confirmed in the literature review (Zhang-Kennedy et al., 2021). Additionally, studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of using games in raising awareness among users (Alotaibi et al., 2016). Game and simulation approaches are commonly applied in an educational context. (Naul et al., 2020) presents a successful combination of storytelling elements and educational games. Engaging students to achieve meaningful learning is one of the defining characteristics of DS. Other emerging technologies listed in Fig. 2 have been identified and classified as "Other." We have social robots (i.e. Zenbo (Chiou et al., 2021) and Furhat (Pasquali et al., 2023) robots) to disseminate cybersecurity curriculum programs and to provide better protection to individuals and companies against cybersecurity attacks. Another emerging category is comics to engage and simultaneously entertain children. Finally, we present story cards (Giménez Ciciolli et al., 2022) as a user-friendly learning tool, tailored to address the digital safety needs of women with refugee and migrant backgrounds. We describe below for each target group the methodology used for achieving the objectives.

K-12 Learners.

Game-based methods use tailored narratives for different groups: fairy tales for preschool-aged, storytelling games for girls, action scenarios for boys, and CTF challenges for college students. These models include traditional Oral Storytelling and Digital Storytelling (DS)(Sylvester et al., 2009).

Digital stories in Games and Video.

Fairy tales in Mobile Serious Game. The mobile serious game, aimed at preschool-aged children, educates about cybersecurity, emphasizing issues such as password complexity. It fills a gap in preschool educational games, contributing to cybersecurity awareness from a young age (Snyman et al., 2021).

Storytelling and adventure game. There is an increase of cyber-crime (in particular online child abuse and sexual exploitation), aimed at teenagers in the African continent. To address these types of threats, a narrative game, named *CyberBullet-Share Your Story*, available on both mobile and personal computers,

was designed and developed to enhance and improve online security education (Mikka-Muntuumo et al., 2018).

Video-based syllabus. This study helps primary school teachers in Africa educate children aged 7-13 about cybersecurity. It promotes computer literacy through games, videos, and courses tailored for different age groups (Solms et al., 2014).

Digital stories.

Stories with social robots. Children's increased mobile phone use exposes them to online risks and cyber threats. Cybersecurity education is vital to raise awareness. This study suggests interactive cybersecurity stories for grades 3-5, using social robots to simplify complex topics (Chiou et al., 2021).

Secure Comics. The study compares digital interactive comics to narrative-only text in addressing children's online privacy risks, particularly geo-tagging photos. Findings indicate that digital visual storytelling, such as comics, effectively enhances children's privacy knowledge and behavior (Zhang-Kennedy et al., 2017).

Comic-BEE. The CySCom project aims to raise cybersecurity awareness among American teenagers (13-17 years old) using educational comics. It utilizes Comic-BEE, a web-based platform, to simplify cybersecurity concepts and provide reusable educational materials (Ledbetter et al., 2016).

Graduate and Undergraduate students.

Digital stories in Games and Video.

Narrative in Jeopardy CTFs. (Chothia et al., 2019) introduces a virtualized framework to integrate Jeopardy-style Capture The Flag (CTF) challenges into a university cybersecurity course. It extends the framework with a narrative component, enhancing adaptability to changing educational needs across course iterations.

Narrative as gamification concepts. Criminal Investigation is a web-based gamified framework specifically for teaching topics such as IoT security skills. Engagement and learning are further achieved by introducing gamification concepts such as storytelling that motivate undergraduate students (**hall2022criminal**).

Storytelling game. CTF challenges offer immersive cybersecurity learning with storytelling elements for undergraduates in the University of Corfu's Department of Informatics. It seamlessly integrates into academic programs, bridging the theory-practice gap for both faculty and students (Karagiannis et al., 2020).

Digital stories.

PrivacyToon. (Suh et al., 2022) highlights the challenge of defining complex privacy concepts and suggests comics as an effective medium for storytelling to address this. It introduces cards to raise awareness about privacy concepts and proposes PrivacyToon to fill gaps in educational comics.

Secure Comics. A survey analyzes user awareness of cybersecurity threats like guessed passwords, antivirus protection, and online privacy on mobile devices. Critical findings reveal a lack of understanding, motivating the creation of an interactive online comic series called Secure Comics (Zhang-Kennedy et al., 2016).

Other participants.

Digital stories in Games and Video.

VR serious games. The study introduces CyberVR, a virtual reality game for cybersecurity education, and Digital Storytelling (DS) for creating educational videos on overlooked cybersecurity topics (Veneruso et al., 2020).

Storytelling video. Internet users often underestimate the significance of various online risks, such as cyberbullying, online fraud, and pornography. This study explores the use of Digital Storytelling (DS) to collaboratively produce educational videos on cybersecurity topics to address this issue (Khalid et al., 2020).

Hyper Media Novels (HyMN). Vulnerable groups like the elderly, youth, and migrants are at higher risk of cyber threats. To address this, HyMN, a web authoring tool, combines narrative, gaming, and non-digital security activities. It offers personalized storytelling to enhance cybersecurity awareness and knowledge among these populations (Heiden et al., 2023).

Comic-BEE. Interactive graphic cartoons are used in a CTF event to raise awareness of digital dangers in cyberspace among professionals. Created with the Comic-BEE online platform, these cartoons engage participants in risky situations, emphasizing the consequences of their choices to educate employees of an industrial company about IT security threats (Barela et al., 2019).

Digital stories.

Storytelling game with a Social Robot. A computer-based storytelling game, named Choose-Your-Own-Adventure (CYOA), exposes the participants to risks and Social Engineering (SE), and a social robot (named Furhat) is introduced that can guide the decisions of human beings (Pasquali et al., 2023). The use of storytelling with robots, very little used in the past (Muñoz et al., 2021), in this experimental context, has positively influenced the behavior of the participants.

RouterJoyVis. (Schufrin et al., 2020) addresses security concerns about home network traffic for laypersons. It introduces two prototypes: RouterJoyVis for motivated users and YoutNet-Story for less motivated users, aiming to increase awareness and involvement in analyzing home network data.

Story Cards. "Story cards" is a prototype aimed at addressing digital security issues among refugee and migrant women. Using dialogue and storytelling, it delivers important information with a focus on accessibility and adaptability to the needs of the target group (Giménez Ciciulli et al., 2022).

3.2 RQ2: Digital educational tools.

Fig 2 highlights and confirms the limitations of traditional education methods in addressing the dynamic nature of cybersecurity. Furthermore, it mentions the various delivery methods suggested by (Chowdhury et al., 2021) cited in the table, such as game-based, video-based, simulation-based training, comics, etc. This provides additional context and insight into alternative approaches that may be more effective in addressing the challenges of cybersecurity education.

3.3 RQ3: Evaluation in educational cybersecurity.

Addressing our RQ3, we describe outcome measures in Fig 3 that have been identified in this review.

Some studies discussed ((Chiou et al., 2021; Giménez Ciciulli et al., 2022; Heiden et al., 2023; Mikka-Muntuumo et al., 2018)) highlight the use of a user-centered design approach as an HCI methodology, wherein the needs of users are primarily considered ((Addone et al., 2022; Berendsen et al., 2018)). The action component of awareness, among the highlighted outcomes, becomes evident as technology has invaded every aspect of our lives and continues to expand its pervasiveness. In(Chothia et al., 2019), collaboration in CTF events is streamlined with a Story Map, which lays out the narrative, characters, and plot. This tool promotes teamwork among participants as they collaborate to tackle challenges and surmount obstacles together. (Chiou et al., 2021) communicated the emergence of cybersecurity education programs that use game-based designs to make learning more engaging and collaborative for students. A game-based approach, including a narrative style, creates an engaging environment for learning security skills and aids students in achieving the learning objectives (**hall2022criminal**). CTF challenges in (Karagiannis et al., 2020) provide a cybersecurity educational context for the students to engage gradually and acquire the appropriate knowledge and skills. Furthermore, during the learning process, they involve integrating various elements such as teamwork and collaborative learning attributes. However, a simulation and virtualization-based experiment failed due to participants finding images distracting and preferred text-only material (Barela et al., 2019). In addition, Virtual Reality (VR) videogames based on an immersive approach offer an interactive learning experience to enhance user awareness of cybersecurity issues and introduce a new approach to child-robot collaborative interactions(Veneruso et al., 2020). Indeed, the use of social robots in cybersecurity presents a double-edged sword. On the positive side, robots can serve as

effective mediums for delivering cybersecurity and social engineering warnings; on the side, some negative observations arising from the experiment suggest they could be potentially misused, for instance, by hackers (Chiou et al., 2021; Pasquali et al., 2023). The remaining studies (Zhang-Kennedy et al., 2017; Ledbetter et al., 2016; Zhang-Kennedy et al., 2016) focused on using the visual comic-based DS in terms of engagement, teaching, and learning. Finally, the authoring tool (Suh et al., 2022) facilitates digital comic creation for educational purposes, effectively conveying privacy concepts, and raising awareness about cybersecurity. In (Khalid et al., 2020), DS is recognized as a potent technological tool for teaching cyber risk awareness and aiding teachers in constructing collaborative problem-solving environments conducive to learning.

Reference	Target	Country	Incident classification	Technology	Authoring	Delivery Methods	Tool/Book name
K-12 Learners							
([30], 2021)	Pre-school Children	South Africa	Intrusion Attempts	Mobile and tablets	No	Game-based	-
([21], 2018)	Children	Africa	Abusive Content	Mobile and Desktop	No	Game-based	CyberBullet - Share Your Story
([7], 2021)	Aged 13-14	-	Information Content Security	Social robot	No	Other (Social Robot)	Zenbo https://zenbo.asus.com/
([31], 2014)	Aged 7-13	Africa	Abusive Content, Fraud, Intrusion Attempts, Malicious Code	Desktop	No	Video-based	-
([36], 2017)	Aged 11-13	-	Information Content Security	Mobile	No	Other (Comics)	Secure Comics Book
([20], 2016)	Aged 13-17	America	Information Content Security	Web-based	Yes	Other (Comics)	Comic-BEE http://securedesicions.com/comicbee
Graduate and Undergraduate							
([8], 2019)	UG	United Kingdom	Information Content Security	Laptop and desktop computers	Not active	Simulation and virtualization-based	-
([32], 2022)	G	Canada	Other (Privacy topics)	Web-based	Yes	Other (Comics)	PrivacyToon https://privacytoon.github.io/
([38], 2016)	G	Canada	Intrusion Attempts, Malicious Code	Web-based	No	Other (Comics)	Secure Comics book
([16], 2022)	UD	USA	Other (Internet-of-Things security, Reverse Engineering, Analyzing IoT Firmware)	Web-based	No	Game-based	Criminal Investigation
([18], 2020)	UD	Greece	Information Gathering	Web-based	No	Simulation and virtualization-based	-
Other participants							
([25], 2021)	Average 25.6 years old	-	Information Gathering	LapTop, Tabletop, humanoid robot	No	Other (Social robot)	-
([35], 2020)	Aged 24-34	Italy	Information Gathering, Intrusion Attempts, Intrusions	Oculus Rift, Leap Motion	No	Game-based	CyberVR
([19], 2020)	Teachers	India, Chine, Malaysia	Intrusion Attempts, Malicious Code	Web-based	No	Video-based	Powtoon https://www.powtoon.com/ , Pixtoon https://www.pixton.com/welcome , Plotagon https://www.plotagon.com/
([32], 2022)	Teacher	Canada	Other (Privacy topics)	Web-based	Yes	Other (Comics)	PrivacyToon
([17], 2023)	Vulnerable groups	-	Other (Safe internet)	Web-based	Yes	Game-based	Hypermedia Novels (HyMN)
([29], 2020)	Laypersons	-	Information Gathering	Web-based	No	Game-based	RouterJoyVis, YourNetStory
([15], 2022)	Vulnerable groups	Germany	Intrusion Attempts, Abuse Content, Fraud	Mobile	No	Other (Story cards)	-
([5], 2019)	Employees	-	Other (B&R, PLP, PassM, WSD, PatchM)	Web-based	Yes	Simulation and virtualization-based	Comic-BEE http://securedesicions.com/comicbee

Figure 2. A state-of-art of the study.

Reference	Participants	Evaluation	Context
K-12 Learners			
([21], 2018)	Students, teachers, parents, and game developers	Requirements collection	Workshop
([7], 2021)	5 Teachers	Validate learning materials, collaborative learning	-
([36], 2017)	22 Child and parents pairs	Engagement and learning	Home
Graduate and Undergraduate			
([8], 2019)	Students	Engagement, awareness and collaborative learning	University
([32], 2022)	18	Awareness, engagement and learning	Remotely
([38], 2016)	52	Awareness, engagement and learning	University
([16], 2022)	36	Engagement and learning	University
([18], 2020)	94	Awareness, engagement, and collaborative learning	University
Other participants			
([25], 2021)	19	Awareness and engagement	Remotely
([35], 2020)	40	Awareness, engagement, and collaborative learning	University
([19], 2020)	28	Awareness, engagement, and collaborative learning	-
([15], 2022)	-	Validate learning materials	-
([5], 2019)	20	-	Company

Figure 3. Focus on specific target groups (peach-colored rows) for collecting or validating requirements for designing and developing educational tools.

4 Conclusions and Further Research

Cybersecurity is increasingly pervasive and has a global impact on nearly everyone. People now live in a cyber world where all data and information are stored digitally and online. Therefore, there is a great need for all people to become educated on the dangers and consequences of using technology, in which they are immersed on a daily basis. Digital storytelling fully responds to the characteristics we have outlined for CSE: holistic, collaborative, and dynamic. The aim of our work is to investigate the state of the art of awareness and engagement in cybersecurity through storytelling, targeting all age groups. An SLR (Sağlam et al., 2023) has focused on cybersecurity education for children under 18, analyzing various methodologies, including storytelling. Our literature review addressed three research questions through an analysis of 18 educational programs drawing more substantial conclusions and recommendations. First, we addressed RQ1, which reveals that delivery methods according to (Chowdhury et al., 2021), consistently incorporate elements of storytelling and are effective for every identified target group.

In the CSE, factors such as engagement, feedback, and narrative play crucial roles in the success of digital games. Additionally, educational comics, including comic strips, interactive comics, and storytelling such as a pedagogical approach can engage students in deep and meaningful learning. Second, we addressed RQ2 by investigating computer-based methods for cybersecurity education, including game-based learning and comics, tailored for each target group. This exploration helped us identify and confirm the limitations of traditional educational methods in effectively addressing the dynamic nature of cybersecurity. Third, we addressed RQ3, which focuses on measuring outcomes in studies that even experimented with a small number of participants. The learning activities proposed in these programs target the domain of information security, emphasizing engagement, awareness, and collaborative learning. Additionally, other studies underscore the utilization of a user-centered design approach (Addone et al., 2021; Quah et al., 2022) as HCI methodology, wherein the needs of users are primarily. The evaluation of the study appeared heterogeneous due to few experiments involving a small number of participants, consequently limiting in-depth critical analysis. However, the authors have previously addressed this aspect in a critical analysis and synthesis of findings documented in (Citro et al., 2024), aiming to provide an overview of current practices regarding approaches, tools, and assessments for raising awareness about cybersecurity through storytelling, based on an SLR.

Replication package. The entire PRISMA workflow is man-

aged in JabRef tool² reference manager, which ultimately produces an HTML file with further motivations for all the examined papers and the SLR repository is available on Zenodo public repository³.

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² <https://www.jabref.org/>

³ The SLR repository (replication package): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11843887>

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